

Control of leaf blast by treating seeds with CGA49104. Left, 6-week-old plants from untreated seed; right, 6-week-old plants from seed treated with CGA49104 at 8 g/kg seed.

were covered with polyurethane sheets for 3 consecutive nights to create an environment optimum for rapid blast development. The number of lesions per seedling was determined starting at 3 weeks after seeding.

In several preliminary experiments benomyl 50 WP at rates of 8 to 40 g/kg

seed gave 71 to 100% leaf blast control for 3 to 5 weeks. Effective as seed treatments in preliminary screening trials were CGA40104 50 WP (Ciba-Geigy Werke Schweizerhalle AG, Switzerland), PP389 (4,5-dihydro-4-methyltetrazole [1,5-a quinazolin-5-one], Imperial Chemical Industries, Ltd., Fernhurst,

England), and thiophanate-methyl.

Several experiments were conducted to compare the effectiveness of the four fungicides as seed treatments.

All four fungicides controlled leaf blast (see table). CGA49104 was the most effective and benomyl 50 WP, the least. Seed treatment with CGA49104 reduced blast by as much as 99% at both the 8 and 4 g/kg seed rate 6 weeks after seeding (see figure). The PP389 and thiophanate methyl formulations resulted in 97 and 72% control of blast, respectively. Phytotoxicity was noted with the higher rates of benomyl 50 WP, CCA49104, and PP389. Plants treated with benomyl 50 WP and PP389 at 40 g/kg seed showed temporary blighting of the leaf tips. The treatment with CGA49104 at 16 to 40 g/kg seed showed slightly delayed germination. At 32 to 40 g/kg seed, the fungicide slightly reduced percentage of germination.

The results suggest that treatment with several fungicides already available commercially or being developed can control leaf blast to acceptable levels early in the growing season. Furthermore, expanded fungicide screening may identify compounds that protect against leaf blast throughout most of the season, or that control blast completely throughout the season, by the relatively inexpensive seed-treatment technique. ■

Histochemical studies of the toxicity of carbofuran to brown planthopper

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Brown planthoppers (BPH) treated topically with carbofuran exhibited typical symptoms of carbamate insecticide poisoning: hyperactivity, convulsion, and paralysis.

On the basis of ED₅₀ (mean effective dose) and LD₅₀ (mean lethal dose) values obtained at different time intervals after treatment, carbofuran could reach the site of action within 30 minutes and kill the insect within 2 hours.

Histochemical demonstrations of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity and

inhibition by carbofuran were observed using thiocholine incubated with cryostat-frozen sections of BPH. AChE activity was detected only in the central nervous system (CNS). Its inhibition in the peripheral region of the CNS was closely related to symptoms of carbofuran poisoning. AChE activity in dead BPH treated with carbofuran and two other carbamate insecticides methomyl and MTMC — was recovered. On the other hand, its inhibition by diazinon was more obvious; after the death of the BPH no recovery of AChE activity was detected.

The similarity in patterns of inhibition of AChE activity in both brain and thoracic ganglia indicated that carbofuran was translocated throughout the body via the hemolymph.

The preferential inhibition of the

peripheral AChE activity of CNS was due, not to differential penetration of carbofuran to the site, but probably to the difference in sensitivity or intrinsic activity of AChE located in the peripheral and central regions.

In vitro experiments showed that AChE from the thorax of the BPH was more susceptible to carbofuran inhibition than that from the head. ■

Parasitic nematodes in continuously cropped uplands

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Plant growth and vigor progressively